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Thematic and geographical biases in the mention of research articles by blogs and news in three altmetric providers

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Introduction

Altmetric data providers are becoming fundamental services for altmetric studies. These platforms allow to obtain metrics about the societal impact of research papers. Specially, these services provide a singular endpoint to track the mention of research articles by blogs and news outlets, exploring the connection of the research activity with media and how academic outputs are assessed by the general audience.

However, in the three most relevant providers (Altmetric.com, PlumX and CED), mentions from blogs and news usually come from a curated list of media (Altmetric.com) or from an external specialized provider (Newsflo for PlumX). In both cases, the selection of media could introduce a selection bias that under or overvalue certain publications according to the research area or to the affiliation of their authors. The disciplinary distribution of sources could also influence in the proportion of mentioned articles.

Objectives

The objective of this study is to compare the thematic and regional distribution of a random sample of articles extracted from Crossref and to compare this distribution with the group of mentioned articles by blogs and news outlets from the three most relevant altmetric providers: Altmetric.com, PlumX and CED. In this way, it is attempted to know in which way these sites could be thematically and geographically biased.

Methods

Data

A random sample of 100,529 DOIs from Crossref were extracted in August 2018 to detect the number of publications covered by these aggregators. These publications were obtained from Crossref API with the conditions of being journal articles and published from 2012 (<https://api.crossref.org/works?sample=100&filter=type:journal-article,from-pub-date:2012->

01-01). 2012 was elected because is the sufficient wide time window to capture the impact of the sample in blogs and news.

Next, these bibliographic references were completed with affiliations and thematic categories from different sources. Microsoft Academic (63%), Crossref (14%) and Pubmed (1%) were used to obtain the affiliation of 78% of the publications in the sample. In the case of Microsoft Academic, data were extracted from the SPARQL endpoint (<http://ma-graph.org/sparql>). In Crossref (<https://api.crossref.org/works>) and Pubmed (<https://api.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/lit/ctxp/v1/pmc/>), the public API was used. Global Research Identifier Database (GRID) (<https://www.grid.ac/>) was used to assign organizations to each country.

Microsoft Academic was also used to obtain the thematic classification of the publications. The main advantage of this search engine is that the documents are thematically classified according to their own content and not by the venue. This solves the misclassification problem of citation indexes such as Scopus and Web of Science that assign categories according to the thematic classification of journals. However, only 62.8% of the publications of the sample are indexed in Microsoft Academic. The remaining publications were categorized from Altmetric.com (7.8%) and manually (6.5%). In these last cases, the thematic assignment was done through the disciplinary classification of the venue in Scopus. Due to this, these classifications were adapted to match the Microsoft Academic's system.

Next, this list was searched in the three data providers. In the case of Altmetric.com, Altmetric ID was obtained from the Altmetric API (<api.altmetric.com/v1/doi/>), and then it was used to extract data about blogs and news directly from the web site (www.altmetric.com/details/). This is due to the API only shows counts and not the links and content of these mentions. In the case of PlumX, DOIs were searched in the web site of PlumX (plu.mx/plum/a/?doi=) using web scraping methods. Finally, information of CED was extracted from the API (query.eventdata.crossref.org/events?filter=obj-id:). In the three cases, several SQL scripts were written to scrape the data from websites and APIs. This process was performed during the second fortnight of August 2018.

The list of blogs and news that cite publications from the random sample were thematically and geographically classified (Ortega, 2020).

Results

Biases in the coverage of publications

Figure 1: Share (%) of publications by country in the random sample and in the three altmetric providers.

Table 1. Percentage of publications in each country by altmetric provider. In bold statistically significant differences ($p > .01$) with random sample. Only the first 10 countries by number of publications.

Country	Random Sample		All providers		Altmetric.com		PlumX		CED	
	Pub.	%	Pub.	%	Pub.	%	Pub.	%	Pub.	%
United States	33,275	28.3%	6,616	34.3%	4,493	34.1%	4,142	33.8%	1,061	35.3%
United Kingdom	9,590	8.2%	1,981	10.3%	1,435	10.9%	1,196	9.8%	341	11.4%
China	8,519	7.3%	698	3.6%	363	2.8%	465	3.8%	81	2.7%
Germany	6,540	5.6%	1,109	5.7%	786	6.0%	648	5.3%	178	5.9%
Japan	4,908	4.2%	573	3.0%	363	2.8%	351	2.9%	69	2.3%
Canada	4,675	4.0%	968	5.0%	678	5.1%	600	4.9%	153	5.1%
France	4,259	3.6%	708	3.7%	492	3.7%	456	3.7%	105	3.5%
Australia	3,721	3.2%	727	3.8%	537	4.1%	452	3.7%	125	4.2%
Italy	3,237	2.8%	514	2.7%	338	2.6%	343	2.8%	66	2.2%
Spain	2,743	2.3%	388	2.0%	274	2.1%	220	1.8%	50	1.7%

Figure 1 shows the distribution of publications by the first ten countries in the original random sample in comparison with the three principal altmetric providers. Results show that altmetric providers are biased in favor of English-speaking countries. Thus, while the United States share 28.3% of publications in the sample, 34.3% of these are mentioned in some altmetric providers, being Crossref Event Data the site with the highest proportion of american papers (35.3%). This same thing occurs with the United Kingdom, Canada and Australia, which are overrepresented in the altmetric providers. For instead, the United Kingdom contributes 8.2% of publications to the sample, but 10.3% are indexed in altmetric providers, being CED again the most biased (11.4%). Canada increases to 5.1% in Altmetric.com and CED, and Australia

reach 4.1% of mentioned papers in these same providers. On the contrary, the most harmed countries are China, Japan and, to less extent, Italy and Spain. China goes from 7.3% of publication in the original sample, to 3.6% in the three providers, being the worst coverage in Altmetric.com (2.8%) and CED (2.7%). Japan (4.2%) descends more than one point in all the providers (3%), more significantly in CED (2.3%). In general, whether all the absolute percent differences between the random sample and the altmetric providers are summed, CED (1331) and Altmetric.com (129.6) are the most biased products, more distant from the original sample than PlumX (125.4). However, distributions among providers are more homogeneous because the differences are smaller, with |4.3| between Altmetric.com and PlumX, |7.2| between Altmetric.com and CED, and |12.5| points between PlumX and CED.

Figure 2: Share (%) of publications by research categories in the random sample and in the three altmetric providers.

Table 2. Percentage of publications in each MA category by altmetric provider. In bold statistically significant differences ($p > .01$) with random sample.

MA categories	Random Sample		All providers		Altmetric.com		PlumX		CED	
	Pub.	%	Pub.	%	Pub.	%	Pub.	%	Pub.	%
Medicine	33,319	22.3%	5,418	25.1%	3,382	24.9%	3,669	27.0%	551	18.2%
Biology	26,552	17.8%	3,972	18.4%	2,491	18.3%	2,596	19.1%	483	15.9%
Chemistry	22,400	15.0%	2,743	12.7%	1,673	12.3%	1,689	12.4%	344	11.4%
Physics	11,517	7.7%	1,426	6.6%	921	6.8%	805	5.9%	246	8.1%
Psychology	10,568	7.1%	2,039	9.5%	1,429	10.5%	1,241	9.1%	350	11.6%
Materials Science	7,693	5.2%	730	3.4%	408	3.0%	455	3.3%	103	3.4%
Engineering	5,694	3.8%	679	3.1%	305	2.2%	457	3.4%	91	3.0%
Computer Science	5,132	3.4%	755	3.5%	333	2.5%	542	4.0%	137	4.5%
Political Science	4,742	3.2%	644	3.0%	484	3.6%	333	2.4%	127	4.2%
Economics	3,926	2.6%	537	2.5%	400	2.9%	304	2.2%	89	2.9%
Mathematics	3,296	2.2%	589	2.7%	315	2.3%	412	3.0%	75	2.5%
Environmental Science	2,855	1.9%	547	2.5%	389	2.9%	291	2.1%	102	3.4%
Philosophy	2,779	1.9%	361	1.7%	254	1.9%	200	1.5%	83	2.7%
Geology	2,294	1.5%	465	2.2%	316	2.3%	260	1.9%	88	2.9%

Sociology	1,981	1.3%	296	1.4%	224	1.6%	145	1.1%	75	2.5%
Business	1,518	1.0%	152	0.7%	103	0.8%	87	0.6%	37	1.2%
History	1,276	0.9%	104	0.5%	84	0.6%	55	0.4%	22	0.7%
Art	980	0.7%	53	0.2%	39	0.3%	24	0.2%	13	0.4%
Geography	638	0.4%	59	0.3%	35	0.3%	34	0.3%	14	0.5%
TOTAL	149,160		21,569		13,585		13,599		3,030	

Figure 2 and Table 2 show the disciplinary distribution of publications from the sample and mentioned in the three altmetric providers. Results shows that altmetric providers include more publications from Medicine (25.1%) and Psychology (9.5%) than the original sample (Medicine=22.3%; Psychology=7.1%). In this sense, PlumX is the service that indexes more articles from Medicine (27%), while CED includes more articles from Psychology (11.6%). To less extent, other overrepresented categories in altmetric providers are Biology (18.4%), Environmental Science (2.5%) and Geology (2.2%). On the contrary, the categories worst represented in altmetric providers are Chemistry (12.7%) and Material Sciences (3.4%), being these differences more significant with Chemistry (11.4%) in CED and Material Sciences in Altmetric.com (3%). According to differences between altmetric providers, once again, Altmetric.com and PlumX are more similar between them (|13.3|), while CED presents more disparity with absolute differences of |20.2| with Altmetric.com and |27.8| with PlumX.

Biases in the mention of publications

A way to understand these biases is analyzing the thematic and geographical distribution of the sources that cite the publications. In this way, it is attempted to observe whether specific type of sources (by region or discipline) are more prone to mention publications from specific research areas or countries. This allows us to explain if the biases are produced by the altmetric providers selecting sources or are also caused by the sources citing particular papers.

Figure 3: Share (%) of publications (grouped by affiliation country of the author) mentioned in blogs and news (grouped by country).

Figure 3 depicts a bar chart of the first ten countries with more blogs and news outlets tracked by the three altmetric providers (x axis) and the percentage of cited articles grouped by country

affiliation (y axis). The geographical classification of blogs and news was made in a previous study (Ortega, 2020). In every country, the largest percentage of mentioned papers are from the United States, with percentages between 21.5% of France and the 34.7% of Australia. Note that in the random sample the percentage of publications from the United States is 28.3%. The second country by mentions is the United Kingdom, ranged from 11.8% of the United Kingdom to 7.6% of India. A table of contingency was built by each country showing the percentage of cited or not cited papers from its own country's media or from foreign countries. Then, chi-square test was calculated to verify the independence of the media citing papers with regard to the affiliation of the papers. Results show that there is not independence of the media when they are going to cite papers ($p < .001$), favoring the citation of papers from their own countries. This independence is less evident in France ($p = .0015$), Italy ($p = .003$) and Russia ($p = .0072$), but perhaps due to the size of the samples.

Figure 4: Share (%) of publications (grouped by main AJSC subject areas) mentioned in blogs and news (grouped by main AJSC subject areas).

Figure 4 shows a similar analysis to Figure 3, but now classifying media and papers by subject areas. In addition, three generic categories were added to group media according to their scope. Science is related to specialized blogs and news in science issues, General is associated to general-interest media such as *New York Times* or *BBC* and Local is used to label media focused on specific regions such as *ABC News 15 Arizona* or *Boise State Public Radio*. Obviously, the results show that specialized media tend to cite publications from their own topic. Thus, Social Science blogs and news cite more Social Science articles (38%); Life Science mention more Life Science (27.9%) and Physical Sciences (26.7%) papers; Physical Sciences media comment to a large extent articles from Physical Sciences (58.2%) and less to Life Sciences (13%) and Social Sciences (11.7%); and finally, Health Sciences cite 40.7% to Health Science papers and 23.8% to Life Sciences. More interesting is the distribution in the three generic categories. Media specialized in science news tend to mention Physical Science (36.7%) and Health Sciences (19.2%). General-interest and Local-interest media show similar and balanced distributions, citing more articles from Social Science (G=32.6%, L=29.5%) and Health Sciences (G=25.5%, L=34.7%). This inclination to mention articles from the same topic is confirmed with the tables of contingency, which confirm that there is not independence of the media when they come to comment articles from the same or different thematic scope ($p < .001$).

Discussion and Conclusions

The results of this study have showed that the coverage of publications are biased in favor of articles authored by English-speaking scientists, specially authors with affiliations in the United States and the United Kingdom. Contrarily, publications from China and Japan are unrepresented. This geographical bias was already noticed in previous studies, which detected very low altmetric impact for Latin-American (Alperin, 2015) and Spanish publications (Torres-Salinas et al., 2018). This bias in the coverage of publications could be attributable to two factors. One internal factor could be that these platforms tend to select more English-speaking media than from other countries or languages. The high proportion of American and British media in these products could explain that English-speaking publications are more mentioned in the altmetric providers (Ortega, 2020). This claim is reinforced after the chi-square test, which has proved that media tend to cite more publications affiliated to the same country than other different. However, other external factor could be that English-speaking media are more interested in scientific news and they include more citations to research articles than other countries (Schmidt et al., 2013).

According to the thematic coverage, distributions are less biased and only Medicine and Psychology articles are more mentioned in altmetric providers than in the random sample. These differences could be due to these subjects are closely related to public health issues and with more presence in media (Bucchi & Mazzolini, 2003). This fact is confirmed when it is analysed the thematic distribution of articles cited by blogs and news. Social Science (32.6%) and Health Science (25.5%) articles are the thematic categories most cited by General and Local-interest media.

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